

Utilizing JIT Python runtime and parameter optimization for CPU-based Gaussian Splatting thumbnailer

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ABSTRACT

Gaussian Splatting has emerged as a powerful technique for high-fidelity 3D scene representation, yet its computational demands hinder rapid visualization, particularly on CPU-based systems. This paper introduces a lightweight method for efficient thumbnail generation from Gaussian splatting data, leveraging Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation in Python to optimize performance-critical operations. By integrating the Numba JIT compiler and strategically simplifying parameters, by omitting rotation data and approximating Gaussians as spheres, we achieve significant speed improvements while maintaining visual eligibility. Systematic experimentation with Gaussian splat sizes (σ) and image resolutions reveals optimal trade-offs: σ values of 0.4–0.5 balance detail and speed, allowing 720p thumbnail generation in 1.8 s. JIT compilation reduces execution time by 156× compared to pure Python (from 336 to 2.33 s), transforming Python into a viable tool for performance-sensitive tasks. The CPU-focused design ensures portability across devices, addressing resource-constrained scenarios like criminal investigations or field operations. Although limitations in Python's inherent performance ceiling persist, this work demonstrates the potential of JIT-driven optimizations for lightweight 3D rendering, offering a pragmatic solution for rapid previews without GPU dependency. Future directions include migration to compiled languages and adaptive parameter tuning to further enhance scalability and real-time applicability.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there is significant effort put into the development of 3D reconstruction technologies. One of the newest technologies, being gaussian splatting, which utilizes 3D Gaussians in order to represent complex 3D scenes. The number of developments on the topic is rapidly increasing, and the technologies have found their place in various domains, from computer graphics and virtual reality to computer vision and robotics [1].

However, Gaussian Splatting involves representing scenes with millions of gaussians, each having several parameters, which can lead to high computational and memory demand [2]. In this paper, we explore a novel approach to address one such challenge: the efficient generation of thumbnails from Gaussian Splatting files by utilizing parameter hyper-optimization and JIT compilation. The main focus of the research is the development of a lightweight CPU based elementary frame extraction method for Gaussian Splatting files that can be ported on a wide range of devices. This frame extraction could find application in user interfaces, machine learning and various areas where speed is preferred over quality. In order to accomplish that the paper explores

Just-in-Time compilation in Python using well established libraries and parameter hyper-optimization.

1.1. Literature background

Several recent studies have addressed the computational and representational efficiency of 3D Gaussian Splatting in real-time rendering and reconstruction tasks. N. Fry [3] investigated the feasibility of executing Gaussian Splatting operations on a graph processor, identifying memory access patterns and rasterization bottlenecks that differentiate it from conventional GPU execution. This hardware-agnostic approach parallels the motivation behind our work, where flexibility and compatibility across architectures are prioritized over peak graphical performance. Additionally, T. Deng and J. Wang [4] proposed GauSPU, a co-designed software and hardware accelerator tailored for real-time Gaussian Splatting in SLAM systems, showcasing potential for frame-rate rendering even in resource-constrained mobile platforms. While both approaches diverge in implementation, they share the goal of decoupling Gaussian Splatting from high-end GPU dependency.

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From an applied perspective, the Technology for Criminal Investigations Research Group [5] has produced several domain-specific adaptations of Gaussian Splatting for crime scene visualization. One such study by Rangelov [6] examined the impact of camera parameters on 3D reconstruction outcomes using Gaussian Splatting and Neural Radiance Fields in indoor forensic settings. Another related work by K. and S. Waanders [7] explored optimization-driven post-processing of Gaussian data for clearer spatial segmentation in evidence analysis. Both studies prioritize scene fidelity, but neither address the runtime efficiency or portability required for thumbnail-level summarization, especially in field scenarios where computational resources are limited. Thus, this paper can be considered a continuation of the aforementioned research.

Parallel work has also begun to investigate simplifications in Gaussian Splatting’s parameter space for faster image synthesis. Tan and Feng [8] introduced a sparsification strategy that merges overlapping Gaussian primitives to reduce the number of rasterized elements. Likewise, Gong and Yu [9] explored the visual trade-offs of discarding isotropic per-Gaussian features like rotation in rendering, noting that the omission results in a small perceptual loss in most cases, while significantly reducing computational cost. These findings support the approach taken in this work, where rotational parameters are deliberately excluded to maintain rendering speed.

The present work differentiates itself by targeting Gaussian Splatting from a minimalism and portability perspective. Instead of enhancing rendering fidelity or accuracy, the method described focuses on extracting single-frame snapshots suitable for thumbnail generation. By combining Just-in-Time compiled routines with a simplified splat model like excluding rotation and treating all primitives as spheres, this pipeline is designed to function under CPU-only conditions without access to dedicated graphics acceleration. This positions the method as an alternative approach within the Gaussian Splatting ecosystem: one that prioritizes responsiveness and compatibility over precision, intended for previewing, field investigation, or batch visualization in constrained environments.

In this paper, we will explore the relation between different Gaussian weights and the impact of the scale and rotation parameter to the eligibility and speed of the frame generation. The main goal of this paper is to find a sweet spot between fast, efficient and eligible thumbnail generation. Moreover, we will explore a concept called Sphere splatting, inspired by the Particle Splatting explored by Adams and Lenaert [10], where the authors propose the use of spheres to efficiently visualize particle based simulation data. The aforementioned sphere splatting means that we will treat each gaussian as a sphere. For the purposes of eligibility we will set the initial radius to the largest gaussian scale and then based on visual inspection tune the scale up or down. Additionally, we will examine the principles of JIT compilation and how they can be applied to optimize Python code for numerical computations.

1.2. Technical background

In this section we will provide a basic introduction to Gaussian Splatting and JIT-compilation.

1.2.1. Gaussian splatting

Gaussian splatting is a volume rendering technique that represents 3D scenes using a large set of discrete 3D Gaussian primitives, which are ellipsoidal particles parameterized by spatial and appearance attributes [11]. Each Gaussian is defined by its position (3D coordinates), rotation (orientation, often represented as a quaternion or rotation matrix), scale (defining the dimensions of the ellipsoid), and color (frequently encoded using spherical harmonics for view-dependent appearance). During rendering a set of Gaussians are projected on an image plane as “splat” primitives. In case of overlapping Gaussians the following gaussian weight function is used to determine their contribution to the pixel value:

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}) = \alpha \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\mathbf{x} - \boldsymbol{\mu})\right) \quad (1)$$

1.2.2. Just-in-time compilation

In the realm of computer science, just-in-time (JIT) or ahead-of-time (AOT) compilation is a methodology of executing computer code that involves compilation during execution of a program, also referred to as at run time, as opposed to before the execution [12–15]. Traditionally high-level code is translated to machine code targeting a specific CPU architecture. Thus, significant effort needs to be put into cross compilation to ensure compatibility. That is not the case with JIT, where a virtual machine provides a consistent ISA for applications, enabling platform-independent execution [16]. This means a piece of software can be ported to numerous architectures. Even though JIT is not as fast as traditional compilation, compared to interpreted languages it can provide a difference of several orders of magnitude in execution time and memory efficiency [17]. For the aforementioned reasons it is the perfect combination of performance and portability for the topic of this paper.

Throughout this paper the correlation between parameter optimization and speed and eligibility of the thumbnails will be explored. Section 2 delineates the methodological approach for implementing the thumbnailer and establishes the criteria for evaluating the impact of various parameters on thumbnail quality and generation speed; Section 3 presents a comprehensive analysis of the thumbnail generation results, incorporating visual examples and qualitative assessments of their efficacy across different parameter configurations; Section 4 offers a comparative analysis of the generated thumbnails, focusing on their suitability and the efficiency of the generation process and addresses the limitations of the current study and proposes directions for future research in this domain; Section 5 compiles the findings to identify optimal parameter settings and provides a concise summary of the research outcomes.

2. Methodology

This research investigates a method for efficient thumbnail generation from Gaussian Splatting files, optimized for CPU-based environments. The approach focuses on balancing thumbnail generation speed, computational efficiency, and visual eligibility through the application of Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation within a Python framework, utilizing established numerical computation libraries.

2.1. Data source

The Gaussian Splatting model employed in this study originates from a dataset of recreated crime scenes, previously utilized in research involving Gaussian Splatting and Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [18] for criminal investigation purposes at [5]. It is worth noting that the aforementioned scenarios are created specifically for forensic researchers for work in real police environments and feature fabricated scenarios. Access to this dataset was granted through prior collaboration with [19] and can be found in Fig. 1. The selection of this dataset was motivated by its complex scene, ensuring the generalization of the proposed method across diverse real-world scenarios.

The Gaussian Splatting model used in this work was captured under daylight conditions, reflecting typical operational settings for outdoor forensic reconstruction. The scene contains a high number of splats, each representing a 3D Gaussian with position, scale, and color attributes. The resulting model is dense and detailed, making it well-suited for testing performance improvements. Its complexity allows for realistic evaluation of rendering speed, especially under constraints where fast image generation is required without sacrificing the structure of the input data.

2.2. Implementation

The thumbnail generation pipeline was implemented in Python, with a modular design that separates computationally intensive math-

Fig. 1. Representation of the Gaussian Splatting dataset.

emational operations from standard Python processes. The implementation leverages the *numpy* [20] library for fundamental array operations and *numba* [21] for JIT compilation of performance-critical functions. The rationale behind this separation is to mitigate Python’s limitations in loop-based operations, thereby maximizing computational efficiency. Parallel processing was deliberately avoided due to the associated overhead in caching and computation management on systems with limited core counts, aligning with the objective of creating an efficient, lightweight solution.

To further enhance rendering speed, the rotation data from the Gaussian Splatting model was omitted. This simplification reduces computational complexity while maintaining a satisfactory level of visual eligibility in the generated thumbnails, consistent with the project’s focus on prioritizing speed and efficiency.

2.3. Thumbnail generation pipeline

The thumbnail generation process overview can be found in Fig. 2, whereas the explanation can be found below:

1. **Camera Setup:** A virtual camera is positioned within the 3D scene, and the view and projection matrices are calculated based on the camera’s position, target, and field of view. The camera parameters were kept constant for the purpose of the performance measurements.
2. **Visible Splat Extraction:** Gaussians that fall within the camera’s frustum are identified and selected for rendering. This culling step reduces the number of elements to process.
3. **Splat Sorting:** The visible splats are sorted by their depth relative to the camera. This ensures proper front-to-back blending during rasterization and prevents visual artifacts in the final image.
4. **Projection:** Each Gaussian is projected onto the image plane using the camera matrices. Gaussians are treated as simple, rotation-less spheres to reduce computation.

5. **Color Blending:** Projected Gaussians contribute to pixel colors based on their weights. A fast approximate blending method is used [11]. This step avoids complex lighting or shading models.
6. **Buffer Update:** The color and depth buffers are updated with the blended colors and depth values, creating the rendered image. As each Gaussian is blended, the corresponding pixels in the color and depth buffers are updated. This allows quick composition of the image without expensive memory operations or per-pixel calculations beyond the necessary.
7. **Image Output:** Once all Gaussians are processed, the color buffer is saved as an image file. This file is used as the generated thumbnail.

2.4. Parameter optimization

In order to identify an optimal balance between computational efficiency and visual eligibility, a systematic parameter optimization process was conducted. This process included three parameters: individual Gaussian Splat size, output resolution and JIT compilation. Since JIT compilation does not affect the output, we primarily tested with JIT enabled to avoid redundant comparisons.

Gaussian splat size (σ)

The parameter (σ) functions as a scalar for Gaussian splat size and plays a central role in determining both the spatial extent and density of each projected primitive. Six (σ) values were selected for evaluation: 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.7, and 1.0. Smaller (σ) values typically preserve finer details at the expense of scene continuity, often resulting in fragmented or sparse thumbnails. In contrast, larger (σ) values increase coverage but introduce excessive blurring, which can obscure structural features.

Image resolution

The image resolution parameter defines the dimensions of the output thumbnail in pixels and directly influences the execution speed during rendering. For the purposes of this study, resolution was treated

Fig. 2. Visualization of the thumbnail generation pipeline using 3D Gaussian Splatting.

as a discrete variable, with selected values corresponding to commonly used standards in digital imaging. These include resolutions representative of low-, medium-, and high-fidelity visual outputs. Thumbnail resolution was varied across three standard output sizes: 480p, 720p, and 1080p.

JIT compilation

To isolate the impact of runtime compilation, tests were conducted with and without the activation of Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation. The Numba library was utilized to compile performance-critical numerical routines, particularly in code segments involving loops, which represent a well-known performance bottleneck in Python [22]. It must be noted that the JIT Compilation comparison was done on a single image, in order to prevent redundancy in the results.

2.5. Evaluation criteria

To assess the quality and performance of the thumbnail generation process, two distinct evaluation criteria were established: computational performance and perceptual eligibility.

2.5.1. Measurable performance

Performance was evaluated using precise measurements of execution time, with particular focus on execution time. These metrics were captured using Jupyter Notebook's profiling utilities and provide a reliable baseline for computational comparison. All tests were conducted under identical system conditions to eliminate external variability and ensure consistency across test runs.

The specific hardware and software configurations used for all tests were as follows:

- **CPU:** AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 5995WX
- **RAM:** 16 GB
- **Operating System:** Arch Linux (Kernel: 6.9.1)
- **Python Version:** 3.13.7
- **Numpy Version:** 2.1.3
- **Numba Version:** 0.61.0

While the tests were conducted on a high-performance workstation, the primary goal of this study is to evaluate the *relative* performance

gain from JIT compilation. The significant speed-up factor observed is expected to be transferable to less powerful systems, where such optimizations are critical for achieving usable performance.

2.5.2. Subjective eligibility

Visual eligibility was assessed through perceptual evaluation involving colleagues with backgrounds in computer graphics and computational imaging. Each participant reviewed a set of generated thumbnails and identified configurations they considered most effective in terms of clarity, structural coherence, and scene recognizability. Their collective feedback informed the selection of parameter settings that maintained sufficient visual fidelity for practical use, particularly in scenarios requiring rapid scene interpretation.

3. Results

In the following chapter, we will present a description of the implementation, present the output of the non-JIT accelerated calculations as a baseline image and results of the parameter optimization.

3.1. Implementation overview

The thumbnail generation pipeline was executed within a Jupyter Notebook environment using Python and relied primarily on *numpy* and *numba* for data handling and performance optimization. The implementation was structured into discrete stages, each contributing to the overall transformation of the 3D Gaussian Splatting data into a 2D thumbnail image.

Camera setup

The rendering process begins with the initialization of a virtual camera. The camera parameters, including position, field of view (FOV), and view direction, were hard-coded to ensure consistency across experimental conditions [23]. These parameters were used to compute the view and projection matrices necessary for transforming 3D splat coordinates into 2D screen space. The use of fixed camera parameters also eliminated variability that could affect comparative performance measurements.

Data ingestion and preprocessing

The initial step involves reading the Gaussian Splatting data from a binary file using *numpy's fromfile()* function [24]. The data is parsed into a dictionary-like structure containing three essential attributes for each Gaussian: position, scale, and color. Importantly, the rotation data, typically used in rendering pipelines to model ellipsoidal orientation, was deliberately excluded. This decision was based on prior observations that rotation had negligible impact on the perceptual eligibility of thumbnails, yet imposed a significant computational cost. As such, all Gaussians were treated as rotationally invariant during projection.

Depth sorting and culling

Following transformation into camera space, all visible Gaussian splats were sorted based on depth. Depth was defined as the distance from the camera along its viewing direction. The sorting was performed in back-to-front order, such that splats closest to the camera were processed last. This ordering ensures proper alpha blending, allowing closer Gaussians to visually occlude those farther away, consistent with standard rendering practices [25].

Splat size computation

Prior to blending, each Gaussian is projected onto the image plane. To compute its projected size in pixel space, only the largest of the three scale components was used. This simplification transforms the Gaussian from an ellipsoid to a sphere, substantially reducing the complexity of

Fig. 3. Non-JIT accelerated generated thumbnail.

the projection step. The size in pixels s is given by:

$$s = \max \left(1, \left\lfloor \frac{\text{splat_scales} \cdot \text{image_width}}{\text{depth}} \right\rfloor \right) \cdot \sigma \quad (2)$$

where:

- *scale* is the largest component of the 3D scale vector,
- *depth* is the z -distance of the splat from the camera,
- *image width* is the horizontal resolution of the output image,
- and σ is a global scaling factor varied during parameter optimization (see Section 2.4)

This formula (Eq. (2)) ensures that all splats maintain a minimum size of 1 pixel and scales dynamically with depth, simulating perspective without introducing expensive geometric computations.

Rasterization and blending

After projection and size calculation, each Gaussian splat is rasterized onto a shared color and depth buffer. The color contribution of each splat is computed based on a simplified weighting function that considers distance from the splat center and current depth values in the buffer (see Eq. (1)). The buffers are updated in a way that preserves compositing order and prevents artifacts caused by overdraw or improper depth handling.

3.1.1. Thumbnail generation

Finally, once all splats are processed and their color contributions blended, the final color buffer is written to disk as a PNG image. This image represents the generated thumbnail and serves as the primary output for performance and visual evaluation.

3.2. Baseline image

The non-JIT-accelerated implementation was used as the baseline for performance measurement. In this configuration, the pipeline executed without any runtime compilation, relying solely on standard Python interpretation. At a splat size of $\sigma = 0.7$, the total execution time was measured at 336 s. The corresponding output image is shown in Fig. 3 and serves as a baseline reference for both rendering duration and visual output under unoptimized conditions.

3.3. JIT acceleration performance

The implementation of Just-in-Time (JIT) compilation using the Numba library resulted in a substantial reduction in execution time. Under identical conditions to the baseline (with $\sigma = 0.7$ and resolution fixed), the JIT-accelerated pipeline completed thumbnail generation in 2.15 seconds. Compared to the non-accelerated baseline time of 336 s, this represents an approximate speed-up factor of 156 \times . This performance gain was consistent across multiple runs and remained stable under repeated execution within the same runtime environment.

3.4. Parameter optimization results

3.4.1. Effect of Gaussian splat size (σ)

A total of six Gaussian splat size values (see in Section 2.4) were tested to examine their effect on execution time during JIT-accelerated thumbnail generation. For each σ , rendering times were recorded across three discrete image resolutions at 4:3 aspect ratio: 480p (640 \times 480), 720p (960 \times 720), and 1080p (1440 \times 1080).

Fig. 4 and Table 1 present the measured execution times as a function of σ for each resolution. The data shows a consistent trend: execution time increases with larger splat sizes across all tested resolutions. This behavior reflects the increased number of pixel updates required as splats grow in screen space, resulting in greater blending overhead during the rasterization process. The trend is most pronounced at higher resolutions, where the total number of affected pixels per splat increases substantially.

The complete set of timing measurements for each (σ , resolution) pair is provided in Table 1. These results serve as the basis for subsequent evaluation of optimal parameter configurations, balancing execution time with visual eligibility.

Visual eligibility was evaluated based on participant preferences, as outlined in the evaluation criteria in Section 2.5.2. Each participant was presented with thumbnails generated across varying splat sizes and resolutions, which can be found in Fig. 5, and asked to select the version they found most visually representative and structurally coherent. The results of this assessment are summarized in Table 2.

Lower splat sizes ($\sigma = [0.1 - 0.2]$) were generally perceived as sharper but incomplete, while higher values ($\sigma = [0.7 - 1.0]$) were

Fig. 4. Execution time (in seconds) for JIT-accelerated thumbnail generation across three output resolutions and varying splat sizes (σ).

Fig. 5. Visual comparison of generated thumbnails across increasing splat sizes (σ) at fixed resolution.

Table 1

Execution time (s) across resolutions and splat sizes σ with JIT enabled.

Res	$\sigma = 0.1$	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.7	1.0
480p	0.9	0.94	1.29	1.53	2.15	3.66
720p	0.97	1.11	1.87	2.33	3.65	6.42
1080p	1.03	1.42	2.99	4.20	7.11	13.31

found to produce smoother, yet occasionally over-blurred images. The most consistently preferred configurations were those generated with ($\sigma = 0.4$) and ($\sigma = 0.5$), particularly at a resolution of 720p. Among the ten participants, 720p thumbnails were selected as the most eligible in the majority of cases, suggesting that this resolution strikes an effective balance between visual clarity and rendering performance. The complete set of visual outputs can be found in [Appendix](#).

Table 2

Participant preferences for splat size σ and resolution during visual eligibility evaluation.

Participant	Preferred σ	Preferred resolution
P1	0.4	720p
P2	0.5	720p
P3	0.5	720p
P4	0.4	480p
P5	0.5	720p
P6	0.4	480p
P7	0.4	720p
P8	0.5	720p
P9	0.5	720p
P10	0.4	480p

4. Discussion

The core of this research centered on two key strategies for optimization: parameter simplification and parameter tuning. For simplification, the rotational parameters of the Gaussian splats were omitted, treating them as simple spheres to reduce computational complexity. For parameter tuning, a systematic evaluation of splat size (σ) and output resolution was conducted. The results clearly indicate that the most effective balance between performance and visual quality was achieved with a splat size (σ) in the range of 0.4 to 0.5 and an output resolution of 720p, which consistently produced visually coherent thumbnails in under 2.5 s.

The experimental results presented in Section 3 demonstrate the practical effectiveness of JIT compilation and parameter optimization in accelerating Gaussian Splatting thumbnail generation on CPU-based systems. When evaluated against a baseline of pure Python execution, the JIT-enabled implementation reduced processing time from 336 s to as low as 2.15 s at $\sigma = 0.7$ and 480p resolution (see Figs. 4 and 5). This represents a 156 \times improvement, highlighting the viability of runtime compilation in mitigating Python’s performance bottlenecks, particularly in loop-heavy numerical routines.

A key trade-off explored in this study is the relationship between splat size (σ), rendering speed, and visual eligibility. As shown in Fig. 4 and detailed in Table 1, increasing σ results in longer execution times across all resolutions. For example, at 1080p, the execution time increases from 1.03 s at $\sigma = 0.1$ to 13.31 s at $\sigma = 1.0$, a more than 12-fold increase. This is attributable to the increased overlap of Gaussian splats in screen space, leading to more intensive blending operations as more pixels are affected by each splat. Conversely, as shown in Fig. 5, smaller σ values (e.g., 0.1–0.2) result in sparse, “pointillistic” images that fail to capture the scene’s continuous surfaces, while larger values (e.g., 1.0) lead to over-blurring that obscures fine details. The subjective evaluation (Table 2) confirmed that the optimal balance is struck in the middle range ($\sigma = 0.4$ –0.5), where the thumbnails are both structurally coherent and generated quickly. This trade-off is fundamental: for applications needing the fastest possible preview, a smaller σ might be acceptable, but for generating visually representative thumbnails, a moderate σ is necessary, despite the performance cost. Unlike GPU-based systems that can absorb this cost through parallelism [11], our CPU-based approach requires a more deliberate balance, demonstrating that acceptable performance can be achieved without dedicated graphics hardware by carefully managing this trade-off.

Visual eligibility, as assessed in Section 2.5.2, showed a positive relationship between splat size and perceived image quality. Lower σ values (0.1–0.2) produced sharper thumbnails with visible structural sparsity, while higher values (0.7–1.0) offered more coherent visual outputs but risked over-smoothing fine features (see Fig. 5). This observation aligns with findings from [26], who introduced a multi-scale 3D Gaussian splatting algorithm to address aliasing effects and enhance rendering speed at lower resolutions, demonstrating that adjusting the scale of 3D Gaussians can significantly impact rendering performance and visual fidelity. The subjective preference study (Table 2) further supports the middle range of $\sigma = [0.4$ –0.5] as optimal, with a clear preference for 720p resolution. This balance was selected by the majority of participants for its combination of structural completeness and fast generation time, which averaged under 2.5 s.

In omitting the rotation parameter from the GS data, this implementation simplifies the Gaussian model to spherical splats. This decision, discussed in Section 2.4, reduced computational overhead without compromising perceptual eligibility in most cases. Although this limits geometric precision, especially in anisotropic regions of the scene, such loss was determined by evaluators, who are familiar with the dataset, as eligible.

While this work emphasizes CPU-only rendering, the approach may complement existing GPU methods in hybrid systems. For instance, fast CPU-based preprocessing could be used to produce low-resolution

previews while high-quality frames are prepared in parallel on the GPU. Furthermore, this pipeline aligns with real-world constraints in domains such as field forensics and embedded vision systems, where GPU resources may be unavailable. The dataset used by Rangelov and Waanders [19] exemplifies such operational conditions, and the results indicate that interactive rendering can still be achieved in these environments.

4.1. Limitations

Inherent constraints of python

While Python’s simplicity accelerated prototyping, its performance ceiling remains a critical limitation. Dynamic typing, garbage collection overhead, and the Global Interpreter Lock (GIL) hinder parallelization and memory efficiency [27]. Even with JIT compilation, Python cannot match the raw speed of natively compiled languages, as evidenced by the 2.33-second generation time for 720p thumbnails, which is orders of magnitude slower than GPU-based alternatives. This restricts real-time applications and scalability to high-resolution or large-scale datasets.

Subjective and limited evaluation

While our visual quality assessments provide valuable insights, we acknowledge certain limitations in our evaluation approach. The participant group consisted of 10 individuals, coming primarily from academic backgrounds, may not fully represent the perspectives of specialized end-users such as AI researchers, forensic analysts or game designers. This demographic composition could influence the generalizability of our findings.

Resolution scalability

Execution times scale quadratically with output resolution due to per-pixel blending operations. For instance, generating a 1080p thumbnail requires 4.5 s, which is 4 \times longer than 480p, posing challenges for batch processing or applications demanding high-resolution previews.

Quantitative metrics and hardware scope

The performance evaluation in this study is primarily focused on execution time. While the results demonstrate a significant speed-up, a more comprehensive analysis including CPU usage and memory footprint would be required to quantitatively validate the “lightweight” aspects of the method. Similarly, the “portability” and “hardware-agnostic” nature of the solution is supported by its software-based approach, but empirical validation would require testing across a broader range of hardware, particularly low-powered devices. The scalability of the method was also demonstrated on a single complex dataset, and its performance on scenes of varying complexity presents an area for further investigation.

4.2. Future work

Migration to compiled languages

Rewriting performance-critical components in Rust or Zig could eliminate Python’s overheads, enabling near-real-time thumbnail generation (e.g., sub-500 ms). These languages offer memory safety, zero-cost abstractions, and fine-grained parallelism, ideal for optimizing splat projection and blending.

Adaptive parameter tuning

Implementing dynamic splat size (σ) adjustment based on scene complexity metrics, such as Gaussian density or depth variance, could automate the speed-quality trade-off. Machine learning models might predict optimal σ values for unseen scenes, enhancing usability.

Integration with GS compression techniques

Leveraging emerging GS compression algorithms (e.g., entropy-coded position data, quantized spherical harmonics) could reduce memory footprint and pre-processing latency, particularly for large-scale datasets.

By addressing these limitations, future iterations could transform the method into a versatile tool for real-time previews, high-resolution rendering, and specialized applications. Thus, bridging the gap between accessibility and high-fidelity 3D visualization.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents a CPU-based method for fast and efficient thumbnail generation from Gaussian Splatting data, focusing on performance optimization through JIT compilation and parameter simplification. While most of the current literature emphasizes GPU-accelerated rendering or custom hardware solutions, our approach is aimed at environments with limited resources where such hardware is unavailable. By removing rotation, simplifying the splat model into spheres, and compiling key routines with Numba, we provide a lightweight and portable solution suitable for practical use cases such as criminal investigations.

The results of our experiments demonstrate that the use of JIT compilation alone resulted in a 156 times speed-up compared to the non-compiled baseline, reducing execution time from 336 s to just 2.15 s. Parameter optimization experiments showed that splat sizes in the range of $\sigma = 0.4$ to 0.5 offered the best compromise between image quality and performance. Image resolution had a significant impact on rendering time, with 720p emerging as the optimal resolution, achieving a generation time below 2.5 s on average. These findings were confirmed in a blind test involving 10 participants, where the majority selected thumbnails generated at 720p with σ values of 0.4 or 0.5 as the most visually representative.

Although Python is not a language typically used for high-performance rendering tasks, our implementation shows that with JIT optimization and careful design choices, it can deliver satisfying thumbnail quality results without any dependence on GPU-acceleration. This is especially important for fieldwork, embedded systems, or other scenarios where portability and accessibility take priority over full-fidelity rendering.

This research contributes to the ongoing efforts within the [5] group in the domain of 3D reconstruction. Future work will focus on integrating this thumbnailer into computer vision pipelines for object detection and scene reconstruction, further extending its use beyond visualization and into automated analysis.

In conclusion, this paper introduces a practical and accessible method for generating Gaussian Splatting thumbnails using only CPU resources. It provides an effective balance between rendering speed and visual eligibility, demonstrating that meaningful performance gains can be achieved in Python through JIT compilation and parameter tuning. This work adds a new perspective to the field of Gaussian Splatting by showing that efficient rendering is possible even in constrained environments.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Evgeni Genchev: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dimitar Rangelov:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Kars Waanders:** Visualization, Validation, Conceptualization. **Sierd Waanders:** Visualization, Validation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. Visual comparison of generated thumbnails across increasing splat size

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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